

Citizen perceptions of energy justice

Deliverable WP4-D1

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About the EnergyPolities Project

EnergyPolities aims to develop an in-depth understanding of citizen participation in the energy transition, the socio-economic and socio-cultural factors which shape it, and the intersections between these and the governance frameworks within which decisions are made. This involves an initial mapping of current patterns of citizen engagement with the energy system, from active consumers to social mobilisation, and from political campaigners to members of community energy projects.

This mapping forms the basis of a typology of citizen participation, which links specific participation forms to the governance structures which condition them and the socio-demographic characteristics of citizens. This typology will subsequently be applied in an in-depth analysis of three case studies of energy projects (two Irish and one mainland EU) that have stimulated significant citizen participation. Integrating both quantitative and qualitative methods, the case studies will reveal linkages between political, institutional and organisational frameworks and citizen participation in the energy system.

EnergyPolities will explore how governance structures intersect with the socio-economic and key socio-cultural factors, including gender, to influence the social acceptability or otherwise of energy infrastructure projects. The business models deployed in each project will be analysed from the perspective of their impact on inclusiveness, gender, democracy and social acceptability; stakeholders' perceptions of distributional and procedural justice will be explored. Recommendations will be developed for how multi-level governance structures, and business models can support inclusive citizen participation and thereby enhance the social acceptability of the energy transition.

For more information see <https://www.ucc.ie/en/energypolities/>

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is the first of two reports from *Work Package 4 – Synthesis*. It has the goal of establishing a clear understanding of what ‘energy justice’ is in practice for different stakeholders and subsequently develop and validate an extensive framework, based on empirical evidence, outlining the complex factors affecting the social acceptability of energy projects. This deliverable identifies social justice issues affecting the social acceptability of the projects. Particularly, the report operationalises the energy justice framework to disentangle the ways in which benefits, and ills related to the projects are distributed, remediated and victims recognised. The themes explored in this deliverable will support effort undertaken as part of *WP4-D2 Framework of social acceptability factors of energy projects*, by analysing how different actors in each of the project’s case studies stake their claims for inclusion in decision-making and for recognition of their identities and interests. In addition, the degree to which they feel these demands are met by current governance structures, and the way they articulate perceptions of fairness/unfairness and justice/injustice are also examined.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

The EnergyPolities project aims to develop a deeper understanding of citizen participation in the energy transition, the socio-economic and socio-cultural factors which shape it, and the intersections between these and the governance frameworks within which decisions are made. Drawing from case studies, this report aims to develop a practical understanding of the meaning of ‘energy justice’ for different stakeholders, from which to develop a framework of factors affecting the social acceptability of energy projects. The three case studies at the centre of our research are:

- Corrib Gas project in Co. Mayo, Ireland, which involves the development of the Corrib Gas field, and construction of the natural gas pipeline and a gas processing plant.
- Grid Link proposal by EirGrid to upgrade transmission infrastructure in the south and east of Ireland, involving a fully overhead 400kV HVAC line.
- Ternitz citizen solar power project in lower Austria, which saw the local municipality partner with industry and individual citizens to realise distributed solar power in the city.

Work Package 4 - Synthesis of the EnergyPolities project aims to establish a clear understanding of what ‘energy justice’ is in practice for different stakeholders and subsequently develop and validate an extensive framework, all of which remains rooted in empirical evidence drawn from data gathered as part of *Work Package 2 – Stakeholder Mapping and Engagement*.

This deliverable, *WP4-D1 – Report on citizen perceptions of energy justice*, identifies social justice issues affecting the social acceptability of the projects. Particularly, the report aims to operationalise the energy justice framework to disentangle the ways in which benefits, and ills related to the projects are distributed, remediated and victims recognised

This report should be considered in conjunction with the following deliverable *WP4-2 – Framework of social acceptability factors of energy projects*, which provides an analysis of social acceptability as presented in the literature and compares these perspectives to experiences in the three case studies. Together, the two WP4 deliverables offer a synthesis of what constitutes ‘energy justice’ in practice for different stakeholders and a comprehensive framework of the factors affecting the social acceptability of energy projects.

1.2 Background

This deliverable constitutes part of the research outputs of Work Package 4, which explores how stakeholders attempt to ‘stake their claim’ for inclusion in the decision-making process of energy infrastructure projects. The report examines the means through which stakeholders establish recognition of their identities and interests, the extent to which they believe their demands are met by current governance structures, and how they communicate their perceptions of both justice/injustice and fairness/unfairness. The deliverable forms the basis for the second deliverable from, which will apply those alternative views of ‘energy justice’ and synthesises the key findings from the three foundational case studies into a framework of factors impacting the social acceptability of energy projects.

1.3 Structure of the document

The report is divided into five sections as outlined below:

1 – Introduction, presents an overview of the report, details the background to the work, provides context for the task undertaken, describes the research aims and objectives and presents the structure of the document.

2 – Theoretical framework, presenting a review of the literature relating to social acceptance and energy justice.

3 – Methodology, outlines both the research strategy and subsequent research methodology that has been designed for the deliverable.

4 – Discussion, explores perceptions of energy justice, across three tenets of energy justice arising from the engagement with the respondents associated with the three case studies, and draws some initial insight towards building a framework of factors affecting the social acceptability of energy projects

5 – Conclusions, summarizing the key findings of the report and clarifying how these relate to the EnergyPolities project as a whole.

2 *Theoretical Framework*

2.1 Social Acceptance of Energy Infrastructure

Since the 1990s, social challenges related to energy infrastructure have generated a large body of research in a range of different national and cultural contexts. This literature review will focus on the

concepts of social acceptance and its links to participation and community engagement in energy developments. The section concludes that perceptions of fairness have a strong influence on how people perceive the outcomes of energy infrastructure projects.

2.1.1 SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Many actors involved in the energy system (including government agencies and energy developers) see the deployment of energy infrastructure as fundamentally a technical intervention. Such an approach entails conceiving of 'fixes' to address instances in which social acceptance is low (Ellis & Ferraro, 2016). However, this section argues, it is crucial to look at social acceptance with a deeper consideration of society's relationships with technology and the diverse power dynamics that undercut those relationships. These dynamics have an impact on the way we serve the future needs of communities and the wider global society. This section will examine key concepts used to conceptualise social acceptance and present the characterisation of the concept for this report.

Social acceptance has been a long-standing debate in the study of industries such as nuclear power, waste facilities, and hydro-electric schemes. Carlman (1984) was the first scholar who went beyond the mere study of public opinion to define social acceptance in relation to wind power. In a study on acceptance among policymakers, she pointed out that siting turbines was also a political matter. This has become a significant point of discussion in this field of study (Fournis & Fortin, 2017).

However, defining 'social acceptance' as a concept has faced validity and normative difficulties. For instance, Ricci *et al.* (2008) argue that the concept is too narrow since it denies other dimensions of how people relate to new technologies. Batel *et al.* (2013) suggest that the concept perpetuates a normative top-down perspective on people's connection to energy infrastructure, and ignores other types of relationships such as support, uncertainty, resistance, or apathy. Szarka *et al.* (2012) question the 'acceptance' literature since they argue that it fails to permit host communities to decide not to 'accept' an energy project proposed by third parties, who often are large corporations that seek to acquire profit beyond sustainability goals.

Despite this criticism, new frameworks have attempted to approach the concept as a complex social phenomenon. For instance, Wüstenhagen *et al.* (2007) break the concept into issues of socio-political acceptance, market acceptance, and community acceptance. Socio-political acceptance is defined as broad-based support for energy infrastructure among policymakers, the public, and other significant stakeholders. Public opinion surveys are one sign of socio-political support, but one may also consider policy support as an indicator of broad-based socio-political acceptance. Market acceptance refers to energy technology adoption by consumers, investors, and the energy

generation industry. At some levels, this is a reflection of technological maturity and reliability such that utilities and investors are willing to make significant investments in energy projects and consumers believe that these projects will not jeopardize ready access to electric power. Community acceptance is an element of social acceptance that deals with local approval or opposition to specific individual energy projects, particularly by residents, community groups and local government. Community approval (or at least acquiescence) can prove a vital part¹ in obtaining required legal permits and licences for infrastructure such as *e.g.*, wind farms. Consequentially, acceptance by prospective host communities is a fundamental aspect of social acceptance of energy infrastructure. This last element of acceptance – community acceptance – which is the concept on which this research is based, is the notion that typically comes to mind first when one reflects on the concept of social acceptance and energy developments. Sovacool and Ratan (2012) enrich this framework by arguing that each type of acceptance is insufficient on its own to promote approval for renewable energy, and therefore socio-political, community and market interests have to align holistically in order for investors and users to advance energy infrastructure.

Overall, the literature suggests that open, fair and deliberative decision-making that acknowledges power, trust and control sharing, is a key factor affecting the social acceptance of energy infrastructure. Thus, to transition to a more sustainable society, profound changes in energy governance must take place. Energy infrastructure emerges at a time when traditional forms of social and political engagement have been undermined by declining trust in public institutions and businesses. This poses a challenge not only for wider energy and sustainability transitions that require fundamental adjustments to governance and market regimes, but also in the way we undertake research. The conceptual frameworks we use, the roles we play in collecting information, the stakeholders that are included, and the methods used to analyse and deliver information have to be aligned accordingly (Velasco-Herrejón, 2020).

Community acceptance has become a significant point of discussion in the social sciences (Fournis & Fortin, 2017), particularly its links to fairness as an important explanatory factor that superseded former, more simplistic ‘backyard motives’ (Wolsink, 2007). Perceptions of fairness have been shown to influence how people perceive the legitimacy of energy infrastructure siting outcomes; a fairer process that increased the legitimacy of the outcome will in turn advance the acceptance of new developments (Gross, 2007). Similarly, characteristics of community-based ownership that address distributive concerns, have proven to be crucial for community acceptance of energy projects (Bauwens, 2016; Bauwens *et al.*, 2016; Bauwens & Devine-Wright, 2018). The importance of

¹ Whether a formal legal requirement or a strongly influential factor.

inclusive citizen participation from the beginning through deliberative decision-making has also been emphasised (e.g., Agrawal and Gibson, 1999; Aitken *et al.*, 2016; Bauwens and Devine-Wright, 2018; Bell *et al.*, 2005; Gross, 2007; Wolsink, 2007).

However, a systematic study that looks at how justice can inform social acceptance has received limited attention. For instance, Roddis *et al.* (2018) consider the relationship between public acceptance and justice by analysing variables found in the public acceptance and environmental planning literature of inshore wind and solar farms. Bronfman *et al.* (2012) propose a model based on trust in government, perceived benefits and risks. Visschers and Siegrist (2014) also focus on benefits and risks, while Truelove (2012) analyses emotions and personal values. The most recent community acceptance research has analysed case studies of opposition responses to particular wind energy projects, with a focus on the opinions of nearby residents and stakeholders (Devine-Wright & Howes, 2010; Gross, 2007; Hall *et al.*, 2013; Swofford & Slattery, 2010; Zoellner *et al.*, 2008). Nonetheless, these studies use existing variables in the literature that often do not engage local communities in defining valuable definitions of justice, perpetuating a normative, top-down perspective on people's relation to energy infrastructure which characterises part of the social acceptance literature (Batel, 2020; Batel *et al.*, 2013). And finally, even though recent research stresses the importance of looking at power relations that underlie social acceptance processes, there has not been ample research that looks at these positions and dynamics of power systematically (Velasco-Herrejón, 2020). Given these gaps in the research, and the relevant questions raised in the social acceptance literature, this study will look at the profound social, economic and environmental factors affecting the social acceptability of energy projects by proposing a framework that draws from energy justice literature.

In sum, this report will advance research on community acceptance (captured through attitudes toward locally installed technologies) of energy projects by drawing insights from environmental justice, economic philosophy and sociology, to build an analytical framework. As a result, the research contributes to a more coherent and compelling body of theory to address environmental and social concerns.

2.2 Linking Social Acceptance to Energy Justice

The concept of "energy justice" (e.g., Heffron and McCauley, 2014; Jenkins *et al.*, 2016; McCauley *et al.*, 2013; Sovacool, 2013; Sovacool and Dworkin, 2014), founded in the literature on environmental justice, (Schlosberg, 2004, 2009, 2013; Walker, 2012) is an overarching conceptual framework that looks at fairness as an important factor affecting the social acceptability of energy projects. This

concept can be particularly useful to identify ways in which benefits and ills related to energy issues are distributed, remediated and whether victims are recognised.

A central research endeavour within the field of energy justice has been the development of a range of frameworks to identify energy injustice(s) and guide energy decision-making. Three particular approaches have gained traction: 1) the 'triumvirate conception of energy justice', conceived by McCauley *et al.* (2013, 2019) which repackages the classic trivalent approach of environmental justice in terms of distributional, procedural, and recognition justice (Davies, 2006; Schlosberg, 2004, 2009), 2) an eight-principled conception of energy justice framed as an analytical and decision-making tool for facilitating decision-making in energy dilemmas (Sovacool *et al.*, 2017; Sovacool & Dworkin, 2015), and 3) an 'Energy Justice Metric', which seeks to quantitatively analyse energy justice to more effectively translate justice principles into policy formulation (Heffron *et al.*, 2015). The triumvirate energy justice framework is the conceptualisation adopted in this study because it is easier to operationalise than the principled conception of energy justice, which draws on an extensive range of moral theories and perspectives. As for the energy justice Metric, its quantitative nature and top-down construction make it less suited for analysing the identities and interests of people living in local communities.

Distributive justice draws attention to where energy injustices are located (Jenkins *et al.*, 2016). It includes both the physically unequal allocation of environmental benefits and burdens, and the uneven allocation of their associated responsibilities (Walker, 2009), for instance, exposure to risk. Within the triumvirate of tenets of energy justice, distributive justice can be considered as the 'chief topic' of environmental concerns (Wenz, 1989) or the 'substantive justice' that matters in a material sense in terms of allocated costs and benefits (Bell, 2004). This concept raises awareness about the link between the desirability of energy technologies and their location (Owens & Driffill, 2008; Todd & Zografos, 2005), calling for the fair distribution of burdens and benefits between all members of society regardless of income, race, gender, *etc.* (McCauley *et al.*, 2013).

Despite its centrality, distributive justice needs to be complemented by other concepts of justice to understand the underlying reasons for maldistribution. The second tenet of energy justice, procedural justice speaks to the idea of fair processes, and how people's perception of fairness is strongly impacted by the way experiences are lived, and not only the outcome of these experiences. Procedural justice is therefore conceived in terms of which decisions are made, who is involved and who has influence (Walker, 2012). Distribution is inherently political as it is driven by power. Political in the procedural sense provides a stage on which struggles over distribution are played out, establishing criteria for who can make justice claims and how (Fraser, 2007). For instance, literature

on renewable energy technologies siting has explored how exclusive and closed decision-making processes generate conflict in evaluations of observed environmental threats (Grimes, 2005), with opposition activity focused on procedural injustices and a lack of chances to be heard (Wolsink, 2007). Thus, procedural justice promotes equitable procedures and the engagement of all stakeholders in decision-making (Davies, 2006). Three main dimensions or ‘pillars’ of procedural justice are widely recognised as key elements of justice in procedural terms (e.g., European Commission, 1998; Walker & Day, 2012; Yenneti & Day, 2015): access to information, access to and meaningful participation in decision-making and access to legal processes to achieve redress or challenge decision-making processes.

Distributive and procedural justices, however, can only go so far. Recognition justice is a call for acknowledging differences while achieving social equity in procedures and outcomes. This requires the study of social differences, which can be concerned with injustices such as gender, sexuality, race, and ethnicity, aiming to re-value unjustly devaluated identities (Fraser 2007). The tenet may present itself not only as a failure to recognise, but also misrecognise (Schlosberg, 2004). As will be analysed in this report, at the core of misrecognition, there are cultural and institutional processes of disrespect that devalue some people more than others. For instance, social norms, languages and mores can be fundamental to the failure to recognise and respect group differences and can ultimately constitute practices of cultural domination and oppression that are rendered invisible through non-recognition (Fraser 1997).

While the triumvirate conception of energy justice is a useful approach to frame ethical issues concerning energy systems, it has some limitations. First, Wood and Roelich (2020) point to a lack of clarity on what can be defined as justice or injustice. Without drawing on a particular account of what makes an event or situation unjust, it proves difficult to identify which aspects of these situations needs ameliorating (Wood and Roelich, 2019, 2020). Second, detailed descriptions and valuations of different conceptions of justice by the communities themselves are lacking. Indeed, the triumvirate conception of energy justice has favoured a top-down approach to energy justice to enable contributions to mainstream policymaking. For instance, Jenkins (2018) states, *“Energy justice does so by overcoming what may be identified as the ‘naïve’ approaches of environmental and climate justice—the presumption that society would support their ideals—focusing instead on embedding justice in policy. This ‘top-down’ methodology offers the potential for a refined ‘practice’”*. However, Wood and Roelich (2020) raise the concern that this approach may not include the values of activist-led, community-driven movements, which constitute one of the main goals of environmental justice (Schlosberg, 2009, 2004). Justice definitions determined by developers,

governments, academia, development agencies or economic elites may lead to the misrepresentation of local people's everyday concerns.

Furthermore, the energy justice framework's definitions and top-down methods are especially problematic when trying to understand factors for social acceptance. Indeed, the reasoning behind a community's lack of acceptance could be rooted in their personal experiences with injustice in certain situations or events. These experiences may vary from individual to individual, depending on factors related to age, gender, age, race, class and/or place. Aside from high-level concerns over electrification rate impacts relating justice concerns to the wind energy industry, justice-related concerns are most immediate for individuals living in the communities adjacent to energy facilities (Velasco-Herrejón & Bauwens, 2020). A bottom-up analysis is thus especially suited for this study to examine how the lives of people are shaped by the introduction and expansion of energy technologies.

3 Methodology

3.1 Methodological Approach and Data Collection

The world of big, global development tends to oversimplify matters. As such, key ideas such as 'sustainable development' or 'renewable energy' are often at the first moment considered a panacea for all development problems, but quickly become yet another element in the long list of development disappointments (Rist, 2008). Part of the problem is that reality is complex and the exclusive use of a particular method of analysis can at its best provide only a partial picture of the phenomena. For this reason, the contribution given by the mixed methods is fundamental for establishing new ways of facing contemporary development challenges.

As previously described in WP2-D1 and WP2-D2, the approach adopted within the EnergyPolities project for data collection and analysis was predominately qualitative in nature and supplemented by quantitative approaches as required across the three case study communities. This involved a combination of desk-based research, sourcing national and international data sources and as a primary qualitative research method – the in-depth, semi-structured interview.

Semi-structured interviews help to voice people's passions on the ground and establish stakeholder resonance, which will in turn help the proposed research to sustain relevance (Burns 2007). This research method can also offer a safe space to establish individual standpoints regarding a situation, attitudes, values and feelings (Seale 2012). Semi-structured interviews therefore facilitate insights

into how people of different sex and age groups define, discuss and contest reasons for project opposition and acceptability and associated notions of justice and injustice.

Identifying appropriate informants requires finding individuals who have considerable knowledge of the research topic or organisation involved in the project being studied. Within EnergyPolities, we were able to identify and recruit informants who were able to provide deeper insights into the events that characterised development in each of the case study communities by using desk-based research, telephone calls, and meeting with those in the wider social networks of the potential informants.

While the engagement was greatly impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic and the preventative measures enforced by the government to slow down its spread, the research team managed to conduct fourteen in-depth, semi-structured interviews in total across the three case studies (coupled with one detailed written response² to questions). The spread of interviews across the case studies is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Breakdown of in-depth semi-structured interviews across the three case studies

Case Study	Number	Recording Length	Note
Corrib Gas, Ireland	7	8 h 58 mins	Time taken to transcribe interviews is approximately 9 x times the duration of audio recordings
Grid Link, Ireland	3 (+1 ²)	3 h 58	
Ternitz, Austria	4	5 h	

The in-depth interviews were further supplemented by a number of informal interviews with informants as part of the ethnographic work undertaken in each of the case study communities. While not formally recorded and transcribed, informants knew they were having a discussion relating to the case study topic and were aware of the purpose of their conversation with the researcher team. This material was captured by field notes afterwards. A breakdown of the number of informal interviews is outlined in Table 2 below.

² Two informants (from one organisation) expressed a preference not to have oral interviews and requested that they respond to the questions in written format instead, this request was facilitated.

Table 2: Breakdown of informal, ‘on the fly’ interviews across the case study communities

Case Study	Number	Note
Corrib Gas, Ireland	4	Notes taken after conversation took place
Grid Link, Ireland	5	
Ternitz, Austria	2	

A full list of interviewees is included in Appendix 1 along with descriptions and the case study to which they appertain. Interviewee identifier codes have been generated to ensure the anonymity of all participants, and to provide the reader with information about the informant while looking through the empirical discussions. All names that appear in the deliverable are pseudonyms, on the occasions that they are used, except when explicit consent has been given for using the real name. All interviews and focus groups were held in English, given that all respondents felt comfortable speaking this language.

3.2 Data Analysis

The data were analysed in two phases. First, all semi-structured interviews were transcribed and thematically analysed line-by-line, *i.e.*, the collected data was ordered, categorised and coded in an iterative manner, allowing finding to emerge from the data. Coding was focused on the identification of factors affecting the acceptance of energy projects according to commonly occurring topics. Second, data collected were then paired and jointly analysed using the energy justice conceptual framework.

To build the theoretical framework, a bottom-up compendium of 40 first-order concepts emerged from the systematic coding procedure of the raw data, which correspond to people’s concerns about energy projects planning and development and thus affect community acceptance of energy infrastructure. These were organised into second-order, theory-centric energy injustices. These injustices were then assigned to their corresponding tenet of energy justice – distributional, procedural and recognition – the results of which are discussed in the following section (Jenkins *et al.*, 2016; McCauley *et al.*, 2013; McCauley & Heffron, 2018).

4 Discussion

4.1 Perceptions of energy justice

The installation of energy infrastructure projects in remote and rural communities and regions, such as Erris, Ternitz and Kildare, is commonly regarded as a win-win strategy to ‘ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all’ (UN, 2015), while at the same time creating development opportunities for often marginalised and impoverished groups. Indeed, in recent years rural and local communities around the world have ‘unwittingly’ become ‘protagonists of the energy transition’ (Savaresi, 2019).

However, the adoption of ambitious energy targets has had profound social, economic and environmental implications at scales ranging from local to global and has raised questions about social justice in capitalist societies. Therefore, identifying key social justice issues affecting social acceptance of energy projects has become hugely important in advancing the diffusion of affordable and clean energy.

This section looks at the profound social, economic and environmental factors that affect the acceptance of energy infrastructure projects by drawing from the energy justice framework, employing the distributive, procedural and recognition elements of justice to analyse people’s perceptions of justice and injustice in relation to the selected case studies. In this regard, the deliverable focuses on community acceptance (captured through attitudes toward locally installed projects) rather than socio-political acceptance (captured through general attitudes towards the projects) or market acceptance (captured through the market penetration of a technology) (Wüstenhagen *et al.*, 2007a).

4.1.1 DISTRIBUTIVE JUSTICE

Concepts of distributive justice – how a society or group should allocate its scarce resources among individuals with competing needs or claims – go back at least two millennia (Roemer, 1998), providing perspectives on what is distributed and the principles for a fair distribution. Arrow’s impossibility theorem, first published in 1951, asserts that there is no ordering of possible allocations of resources among individuals in a society given that justness must consider individual preferences in apparently desirable ways. However, during the 1970s, advocates of welfare-based principles (of which utilitarianism is the most famous, with authors such as Bentham, 1790 and Mill, 1863) established that interpersonal comparisons of utility (or welfare, happiness, satisfaction, *etc.*) are possible, and by doing so, individual preferences could be aggregated into a social preference. This proposition of justice was influential for more than two centuries until the social justice theorist

John Rawls (2009) pointed out that utilitarianism runs the risk of overlooking and disregarding systematic discrimination against some individuals, particularly minority groups, sacrificing their well-being to acquire an overall higher utility gain.

In his book 'A Theory of Justice' (2009), Rawls argued that the fundamental idea of social justice should be fairness in the distribution of primary goods (such as rights, liberties, powers, opportunities, income and wealth). He proposed that the notion of distributive fairness can be attained from an 'original position' where people can mentally position themselves outside a society in which they know they will be a member but are ignorant of their own competitive advantage or disadvantage in that society. From this position, he asserted, principles of fair distribution can be agreed. He also proposed an alternative distributive principle, the 'Difference Principle', which permits diverting from strict equality as long as the least advantaged in society are better off than they would be under strict equality.

This section looks at the evidence and data across the cases through a distributive justice lens. From this, two significant findings emerged. Though energy projects can bring numerous benefits to the local community, the existence of an upward distribution of wealth towards energy companies and external actors threatens the idea of a just energy transition. Second, the analysis revealed that the perceived degree of benefits received is directly proportional to people's level of concern about the natural environment and climate change. This unveiled underlying reasons for how environmental concerns link to the distribution of economic benefits.

Motivations for opposition to energy projects are not always clear. The literature understands opposition as divided into two strands: simple and complex motives. One thread of simple motives explains opposition using the acronym NIMBY ('not in my backyard'). This idea is based on the assumption that although local communities may be broadly in support of the development of energy facilities, they do not want them placed in their 'backyard' (Bell *et al.*, 2005; Devine-Wright, 2005). This opposition is linked largely to the physical attributes of energy projects, such as visual aesthetics, pollution and noise (see Möller 2006; Williams and Whitcomb 2008; Ciardi and Crum 2010; Hoen *et al.* 2009; Lilley, Firestone, and Kempton 2010). NIMBY motives were assumed in the case of the Grid Link project. GL1 explains how there is a rural/urban divide where people living in the city wouldn't support the construction of an energy project next to their houses such as "...a nuclear plant in Ringsend". However, they would still go on holiday to France and Italy knowing that most of the energy used in these countries comes from nuclear power.

However, a distributive justice lens questions the NIMBY motives by showing that there are more complex motives of opposition. Particularly, there is a divide between benefits gained by local communities and energy infrastructure developers. Respondents related to the Grid Link project explain that the main purpose of the line was not to provide energy for local communities. Instead, the grid was *“to facilitate very large-scale industrial windfarms to be constructed in the midlands”* (GL1). It was suggested by one of the respondents that the size of the grid did not correspond with the local energy demand, particularly on the East Coast of Ireland. Instead, the grids were meant to support wind energy projects that would export energy to the UK and mainland Europe. Moreover, the production was also going to be consumed by international data centres, which, according to respondents, *“were creating a huge demand in terms of the grid for very little job creation, and very little benefit to the Irish economy”* (GL1). In sum, the cost of the grid was “socialised” rather than paid by those who would benefit financially – as GL1 explained: *“They will build the data centre, they will go up the road and buy the wind farm, to say they have green energy, but they won’t pay for the cost of upgrading the grid. That is placed back on the ordinary ‘man in the street’”*. Furthermore, respondents resented the lack of opportunities for local communities to participate in projects that could generate energy for their own consumption, *“Little opportunity for ordinary people. Farmers would do biomass, they have massive sheds. Anaerobic digestion was ignored. No incentive to do it.”* Regrets GL1. As in the case of Grid Link, people who neighbour the Corrib Gas pipeline believe that the project would only provide monetary benefits for developers and the industry consuming the gas, and not the local population.

Community benefits and in a frame of ownership is, therefore, a cross-cutting theme. “I think there should be more opportunity for individuals to generate energy at a domestic level, and farm level, to put it back into the system as well” argues a participant, who states that large infrastructure projects do not have a place in the future, because there must be ways in which communities can participate, own and benefit from the production of energy. “If there was a way for people to produce their own electricity and supply it into the grid, people would probably be much more open to it, because the option is there because it’s not there today” concluded another participant.

On the other side of the distribution of benefits spectrum is the community-led solar energy project in Ternitz. TZ3 assures that the community has benefited from the project not only by receiving interest on their investment but also by ensuring energy savings for the municipality, who in turn can spend these funds on improvements for the community.

In sum, the way in which benefits are distributed is an important factor affecting people’s support of a project. Respondents in Corrib Gas and Grid Link were under the impression that the projects

signified an upward distribution of wealth towards developers. And, on the other hand, people participating in the Tiernitz had no doubt that the project was benefiting the local community.

Furthermore, findings showed how benefits were distributed had also an impact on whether people perceived that the project could contribute or not to addressing climate change and how their involvement contributed to this goal. Respondents who didn't see themselves as directly benefiting from the project saw the environmental benefits of the projects with suspicion. And therefore, didn't consider that their opposition to the project would have negative impacts on fighting climate change. For instance, one of the respondents of Grid Link explained that he rather not be involved in the project since he "doesn't want to grow up on a planet that is slowly overheating because we didn't actually deal with the problem when it arose, and we made a lot of people rich by doing the wrong thing." And, on the other hand, the solar farm in Ternitz, even though community involvement at the start was anchored in expected economic benefits and "It used to be not so much about the climate" explains a director of the municipality, as the project progressed, people became more interested in knowing how their support to the project could have positive environmental impacts, and newcomers to the project are now interested in joining to contribute to addressing global climate change.

4.1.2 PROCEDURAL JUSTICE

Procedural justice speaks to the idea of fair processes, and how people's perception of fairness is strongly impacted by the way experiences are lived, not only the outcome of these experiences. Procedural justice is therefore conceived in terms of which decisions are made, who is involved and who has influence (Walker, 2012). Young (2011), in his critique of the distributive focus, advocates for looking at processes, particularly those that produce and sustain unequal distributional outcomes. She argues that democratic decision-making is fundamental to attaining just outcomes, suggesting that distributive paradigms tend to ignore the institutional contexts that sway or determine the resulting distributions. To understand the distributive outcomes described in section 4.1, one needs to appreciate the contested process of the development of energy infrastructure. This section analyses this process in the three case studies.

Procedural justice literature has long mentioned the importance of looking at power dynamics to understand the processes of exclusion in energy transitions. For instance, justice theorist Gordon Walker (2012) defines procedural justice as the power to affect change and influence decision-making, and Shrader-Frechette, (2002) recognises the existence of unjust structures and procedures of the dominance of one group over others, constraining participative justice.

To analyse power dynamics when looking at procedural justice, this chapter uses Gaventa's power cube (2006) to discuss how forms of power are created, and the levels of power at which they occur to look at how these dynamics form barriers to inclusive decision making when installing energy infrastructure.

Drawing from earlier work by Lukes (2004), Gaventa's approach distinguishes three forms of power that shape the way we look at capabilities: visible, hidden and invisible power. Visible power stands for the observable rules, institutions, and authorities of power. Hidden power refers to the agendas that are pre-set by certain powerful actors to maintain control over who participates and who does not participate in decision-making, as well as to determine which concerns are voiced. Invisible power, the subtlest of the three forms, is shaped by processes of socialisation that are linked to deeply rooted psychological and ideological boundaries of participation that normalise exclusion and inequality among all the actors. Who is involved and what is discussed in decision-making processes is framed in a way that is internalised and accepted by both the powerful and powerless. The argument is that while some forms of power may be understood by observing who participates in decision-making related to energy infrastructure projects, and by who receives benefits and who does not, other perhaps more insidious forms of power shape the distributive outcomes by controlling the agenda, and through shaping what are considered as fair processes and roles.

In brief, to challenge unequal power relations and promote change through participation and inclusive decision-making in energy infrastructure siting, we need to look at the power spaces in which they are found, the level at which they operate, and the form they take. All these dimensions interact simultaneously to affect each other. The creation, opening and closure of power spaces are affected by the local, national and global agendas; whoever creates the space and controls the space decides upon the visibility of power, and all of the previous interactions throughout history shape invisible power, which in turn legitimises the status quo (Gaventa, 2006)

Through Gaventa's power cube, the following section will show how power relations shaped the process of siting energy infrastructure in the three case studies. The three stories will show how power was shared, or monopolised, and how it shifted over time which is key to understanding levels of acceptance for each project.

POWER SPACES

Gaventa sees spaces of power as opportunities for participation, where people can act to influence policies, discourses, decisions and relationships that are valuable to them. Participation can involve not only the right to participate effectively in a given space, but also the right and capacity to shape

that space. Gaventa (2006) explains that these spaces are not neutral but are themselves shaped by power relations. He makes a distinction between closed, invited and claimed spaces. Closed spaces are behind closed doors where groups in power make decisions without consulting other groups. In invited spaces, people are called to engage with authorities, such as the government, supranational agencies or non-governmental organisations. Yet, although these spaces are seen as entry-level in local governments to reach national or global policy, the use of terms such as ‘partnership’ and ‘shared ownership’ by actors such as the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund that are in reference to a ‘level playing field’, may be obscuring inequalities of power resources. Finally, claimed or created spaces are demanded by less powerful actors or created more autonomously as places where people gather to debate, discuss and resist power holders outside institutionalised arenas. It is thus essential to examine the spaces of participation offered in energy projects’ planning and development, and ask how they are created, whose interests are considered, and what the terms of engagement are.

Spaces for community participation are often not defined at the outset of the project, and the dynamics between stakeholders will define how this participation occurs and whether it will drive social acceptance of energy projects. Respondents from the solar farm in Ternitz narrate how community participation was not initially thought of as central to the project. The main barrier to kicking off the project was financial. The local government had the space and the willingness to engage in the production of alternative energy but did not finance the project. Community participation “*made the project more positive*” TZ2 assures.

In the case of the Grid Link project, GL1 narrates how the developer initially committed to a comprehensive consultation in advance to seek approval of the project, so that communities would become more engaged. However, participants concurred that this engagement needs to be “*proper, as opposed to surreptitious engagement*”. An ad in the paper is insufficient, he explains. Furthermore, this participative space needs to be “*genuine*”, where decisions are made by the community, and not by the developer and the government in advance of the consultation process.

There are also contexts in which, because spaces for participation are closed or insufficient, such as in the Corrib Gas projects, less powerful actors then claim and/or create new spaces. Cornwall (2002) refers to these spaces as ‘organic’ spaces which emerge ‘out of sets of common concerns or identifications’ and ‘may come into being as a result of popular mobilisation, such as around identity or issue-based concerns, or may consist of spaces in which like-minded people join together in common pursuits’. Other work talks of these spaces as ‘third spaces’ where social actors reject hegemonic spaces and create spaces for themselves (Soja 1996). These spaces range from ones

created by social movements and community associations to those simply involving natural places where people gather to debate, discuss and resist, outside of the institutionalised policy arenas.

In the Grid Link project, community groups created participation spaces without knowing that they were starting processes of organisation. For instance, the equine industry published information disapproving of the project in equine journals, farmers visited other farms to inform of potential impacts of the project, and meeting groups were organised in local schools. Furthermore, the Irish Georgian Society submitted two letters to the project developer EirGrid highlighting sites of architectural heritage importance in Kildare and Wexford, as well as outlining concerns about the methodology of identifying feasible corridors in the project. This initial submission created a new channel of communication between the Society and the developer.

In the Corrib Gas project, community participation in decision-making was not offered as an option by the developer or the government. Therefore, it was up to community members to decide to what extent to engage and how. CG2 explains how tensions arose when making this decision: *“...some people supported non-violent direct action, other people didn’t think that was a good way to go. Some people liked protest, thought that was essential. Other people thought protest would alienate the support.”*

As the project developed, participation spaces were claimed through protest as a journalist explains: *“...there were protests, guards getting injured, Republican³ elements got involved, fairly heavily anarchist groups, intimidation of those who were in favour, I mean it got hot and heavy. It really was, it tore families asunder, it was basically a civil war down there”* (GL3).

For instance, a group of farmers organised to watch the entrance gates to the project so that these were not opened by the developer for six months. Another participant resisted through a hunger strike. As described in WP2-D1 five of these farmers were jailed. Because public spaces for participation were closed, and therefore avenues for participation had to be claimed, protestors decided to counter restricted spaces for deliberation by offering a welcome for participation in the protest to all the groups that would support them. They *“absorbed all outsiders and accommodated them without any problem. And everyone had a common adversary which dominated people’s thinking and so it all worked at that level”* CG2 recounted. The ethos was: *“Look we’re all in this together, not everyone has to do the same thing, not everyone has to have the same level of commitment but there’s room for everybody. So, if you just want to write letters that’s okay. And if*

³ In a lot of Irish discourse and specifically in this context, “republican” is meant as Humphreys reports as a radical, potentially violent iteration of nationalism (2020)

you want to sign a petition that's okay, and if you want to do a protest somewhere that's okay. And we're all the one" (CG2).

However, as the campaign scaled up, debates within the community arose about which and even whether claimed spaces were appropriate. Because he was the spokesperson, CG2 recounts how people would call saying either *"You have to stop the protests, it's killing our community"* or *"you have to have more protests, this is the only way. This is really working"*.

In sum, in all three case studies, it was agreed that a level of community participation is needed for the successful development of energy projects. As efforts are made to widen participation, the aim is to move from closed spaces to more 'open' ones and to create new spaces which may be conducive to meaningful deliberation. However, the way the community is invited to participate and by whom can be decisive in whether people decide to participate or not and accept a particular project.

FORMS OF POWER

According to Gaventa, three forms of power pose challenges for civil society to participate meaningfully in decision-making about energy projects: visible, hidden and invisible. Visible power includes observable rules, institutions, and authorities of power. Strategies for transformation within this form of power attempt to change the 'who, how and what' of policymaking and the policy process (Gaventa, 2006). Hidden power refers to the agendas that are pre-set by certain powerful actors to maintain control of who does and does not participate in decision-making, as well as whose concerns are voiced.

For TZ3 it was clear that the hidden agenda of the ruling party in Ternitz was to generate political capital from the photovoltaic project. However, he found this agenda acceptable since the project was *"essentially good"*. However, even though in this case the respondent was satisfied with the municipality's plan, these hidden agendas, have made community members sceptical of new projects and often decide not to invest.

Furthermore, obscure political agendas that are aligned to different conceptions about the significance and prevalence of climate change are still playing a role in government decision-making when proposing these projects. For instance, TZ3 explained that the FPÖ (Freedom Party of Austria) denies the existence of climate change and therefore the local councillors from this party would oppose the project. Whoever, since they have a smaller representation in the municipality, they decided to withdraw their opposition claims.

In the case of the Corrib Gas project, one way in which hidden power was exercised was through the threat of imprisonment. For instance, conflict observers had to wear badges and *“put things in our backs”* to make sure that they were not mistaken by protesters and detained because *“there were so many protesters arrested, and you have to be careful because you will spend your lifetime in court on minimal charges. And it keeps you off the road and you might be told not to go back to that area again”* (CG1).

Finally, invisible power, the subtlest of the three forms, is shaped by processes of socialisation that are linked to deeply rooted psychological and ideological boundaries of participation that normalise exclusion and inequality among all actors. Who is involved and what is discussed in decision-making processes are framed in a way that is internalised and accepted by both the powerful and powerless (Gaventa, 2006).

One way in which invisible power was exercised, in the case of the Corrib Gas project, was by community members not being able to openly express their reasons for opposing the project. CG2 relates how reasons for opposition were associated with the attachment to the place and the local form of life such as memories of how *“we took seeds out of cow dung”*. Because this discourse is not accepted as an acceptable reason for opposing a project, protesters had to instead frame their protests as a need for the *“protection of their environment”* as well as their *“health and safety”*. Furthermore, hidden power related to imprisonments could also become invisible by having an influence on the actions of protesters' children. By watching their parents being jailed, *“the beatings and the rest”*, explains CG1, they will be terrified of raising their voices against projects in the future.

Invisible power in the Ternitz photovoltaic project was prevalent in the way financial information between community members was shared (or not). For instance, TZ3 did not know who else was involved in the project because he was uncomfortable asking other community members about matters that involved money *“people don't talk about money generally”*. Moreover, one of the main reasons for community members' non-participation in the project was due to the fear of sharing their financial situation with investors *“It would be like showing one's bank account”*. Furthermore, political parties and the media had an important impact on how people felt about participating in energy communities *“Unfortunately the newspapers have the biggest market share in opinion forming and influenced people”*.

Overall, the way in which power spaces were created and forms of power exercised was key to understanding people's perception of the justice or injustice of siting processes and their associated levels of acceptance. Open and genuine spaces for participation were key to gaining acceptance in

the case of Ternitz, while invited spaces that were not “*genuine*” contributed to the scepticism of people living near to the proposed Grid Link project. Finally, the restricted participation spaces were conducive to claiming more open spaces through protests in the Corrib Gas case.

4.1.3 RECOGNITION JUSTICE

Social justice is often understood in terms of distributive and procedural claims as seen in sections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2, respectively. However, while theories of distributive justice offer models and procedures by which distribution may be improved, these do not examine the social, cultural, symbolic and institutional conditions underlying unfair distributions and processes in the first place (Young, 2011). This section argues that the reason for poor distribution and lack of due diligence in the energy industry can be found in the lack of recognition of cultural differences. Evidence collected through this research suggests that respondents from Corrib Gas and Grid Link perceive that their culture is being threatened by infrastructure siting practices that reproduce colonial forms of discrimination.

Honneth sees recognition as a way of pointing out differences that have been disregarded, in the hope of showing that apparent neutrality in the state and society is by no means neutral but based on a partial interpretation of citizenship that privileges specific groups. Under these conditions, members that do not fit a hegemonic identity (*e.g.*, male-dominated, white, heterosexual, individual) are discriminated against (Taylor, 1994: 42). Fraser (1998) propose looking at these differences through three concepts: (1) Cultural domination (being subjected to patterns of interpretation and communication associated with another culture alien to one’s own), (2) Non-recognition (being rendered invisible via the authoritative practices of one’s culture), and (3) Disrespect (being depreciated in stereotypic public cultural representations and/or everyday interactions). Drawing from the literature (Fraser, 2000; Honneth, 1996; Young, 2011), this section looks at recognition justice as a call for acknowledging differences while achieving social equity in procedures and outcomes. This requires the study of social differences, through gender, sexuality, race, and ethnicity, aiming to re-value unjustly neglected identities.

In the case studies of Corrib Gas and Grid Link, participants perceived certain actions from developers as cultural domination, where they are being subjected to patterns of interpretation and communication that are not in line with their local culture. Corporations, a respondent from the Corrib Gas project explains, are “*legal beings that are not cultured. They don’t have the local accent; they don’t know the local culture and don’t have the timelines of the local culture*” (CG2). The reference to accents here was an allusion to not being of the community.

Moreover, they felt that there were disrespected in their interactions with the developer because *“there was no recognition of them as people at all”,* recounts CG1, *“...it means that neither the state nor the police at the time had any notion of how to react to protest except as kind of like bulldogs...”* *“...the had this in the media there was ‘ah sure they’re very poor over there, they’ve nothing”*.

They also didn’t feel listened to. In the Grid Link project, people were open to listening to the developer’s proposal and did not initially oppose the energy project, they didn’t feel this same attitude from the developer whose suggestions for installing new renewable plants such as wind farms were not in the line of those that would be accepted by the local population such as biomass. And, in the Corrib Gas project, even though developers tried to engage with the local population *“they always came on the supposition that we are right and you are wrong”* (CG1).

Findings also highlight that acceptance of energy projects is shaped by identity struggles that aim not only for a more favourable distribution of goods but also for the recognition of particular identities. In the case of Corrib Gas, this identity was connected to a sense of place, which, according to (Massey 2005: 130) can be understood as an *“integration of spaces and time”*. Place is something that one interprets, moves to, indeed, moves through. It defines and is defined through experiences, and through these contexts, place is both formed and contested. For the protesters to the Corrib Gas pipeline, it was striking how much the sense of place featured in their discussions. One respondent described a conversation he had with a couple of prominent leaders of the protests where he asked them what the protests were all about and they summed up their involvement to him as follows, essentially *‘...this is all about memories, the footsteps, our footsteps are around this property, we grew up here’* (CG2). A self-declared motivating factor was the individual and familial histories that intertwine with the physical landscape to inform local perceptions of place. As Stephanie Taylor (2010) suggests, the place where people live their lives still plays an important role in their identity, especially within the narratives they use to express who they are. And while a *“person’s identity (‘who I am’) is fragmented and unfixed, differing, for example, from one situation to another”* (*ibid.*, 2010: 43) – this can be seen as a process of ongoing, open-ended change – notions of place still act as an anchor for many people’s identity.

A notable example of this is the name local people assign to the area around the Corrib Gas pipeline, which links back to the medieval Norman baronies rather than the more modern county system used today in Ireland: *“Like you have to understand Erris. You have to understand it as a [pause] it’s a very unique area in Ireland because it’s probably the only place I know that still identifies itself as a barony. Baronies are Norman and again this is interesting geographically, baronies are old Norman divisions, and they predate counties, and they are deeper than counties. I doubt anybody in Ireland*

knows what barony they live in. It's a completely redundant idea and in Mayo no-one knows what barony they live in, but Erris people do. Erris is the only place that is distinctive by virtue of its barony. And so, people talk about 'Erris' and it means something" (CG2). It was also a strong factor in defining how local people responded to the pipeline. One respondent described this as an *indigenous sense of place*, where belonging is wrapped up within oneself but also with one's familial history and *"the integrity of a place not being disturbed"* (CG2) by external actors. *"You walk that landscape with him, literally every few footsteps he has a new place name. And in that place name is embedded a story of these people, so the connection of people and place, and people and time and place is very profound here... so their sense of who they are is very rooted in Erris specifically"* (CG2).

Furthermore, it's about claiming at embracing an identity that might not be well accepted elsewhere such as being poor. A respondent narrates how his father came to *"that little strip of land and how they have to save the seeds from the cow dung to reuse them"*. *"They had been very poor... but they have no resentment towards that, that is the way it was"*. In this sense, the struggle for preserving valued identities *"became a battle between the old and the new"* as one of the respondents described it, which can be positioned in conflict with ideas of 'modernisation' or 'development'. Ireland's colonial past has led to the characterisation of people living in rural areas as poor and uneducated. Consequently, overcoming poverty and becoming 'developed' is often linked to the need to abandon *"Part of what we are"* to embrace *"the new era of sustainable energy and the price that has to be paid for that"* (GL3).

This dilemma can be understood through the idea of the modernization theory of development which is an umbrella term for various paradigms that emerged in the 1950s that sought to describe and explain the processes of transformation from traditional or so-called underdeveloped societies to so-called modern and developed societies (Power, 2018). These paradigms are united around a central idea, namely that progress is the universal basis for development, which is conceptualised as consisting of a process of evolutionary stages (Rostow, 1960). In this view, traditional societies are considered as backward, simple and primitive, while Western societies are depicted as ideal economies that have reached the final stage of modernization: the age of *"high mass consumption"* (Rostow, 1960). Traditional structural and cultural features are thus regarded as incompatible with such development and therefore must be overcome.

Participants in the Ternitz project, in contrast to the cases of Corrib Gas and Grid Link, perceive the project not as cultural domination, but as an extension of their self-chosen identity. Because community members are becoming more concerned about climate change and their individual role in the transition to renewables, they see their participation in the photovoltaic project as a positive

form of engaging in this transition. They explain that this pro-environmental identity has been self-constructed and in accordance with their personal values. However, they warn that the media and political parties still play a role in shaping positions of climate change denial, and therefore scepticism towards these projects and polarisation in political discussions. Therefore, respondents in Ternitz point to the importance of the context of neutrality that prevailed in the photovoltaic project: *“was expressly the goal, not to make this a partisan political event, but non-partisan with the invitation of the local council”* (TZ3).

In sum, the concerns of people associated with the Corrib Gas and Grid Link were not only about the unequal distribution of benefits and restricted processes, but also the non-recognition of their identities, natural heritage and culture. These, in turn, have become important factors affecting people’s negative attitudes towards advancing energy developments. Thus, research findings point to the need to embrace a plurality of development visions and identities while acknowledging and respecting them. Echoing the notion of justice as recognition (Fraser 1998), we contend that this act of recognition is required to overcome obstacles of distribution and due process when designing and deploying energy projects. “Difference” needs to be valued to be able to recognise people as equal. Active listening and engagement can aid in pursuing energy projects that are in line with local identities and culture and can be a key starting point to understanding how a socially just energy project can be achieved.

4.2 Insights towards building a framework of factors affecting the social acceptability of energy projects

Section 4.1 explored local people’s concerns about energy infrastructure, the dynamics of siting processes, and how people’s identities are recognized and negotiated during these processes. One main finding that emerges from this research is that communities are not opposed to energy projects or specific technologies. Communities are concerned about how they are engaged, how benefits are distributed and how different identities are recognised and respected: *‘nobody opposed to electricity, nobody opposed to generation. Just the way they were going about it.’ ‘Not don’t want powerlines, we don’t want powerlines in the manner they are being proposed.’* Here, we aim to draw some initial insights of factors affecting the social acceptability of energy projects, which will be covered in a more substantive way in WP4-D2 in a three-tier conceptual model to explore project characteristics, social-psychological and socio-demographic factors influencing acceptance amongst stakeholders in the three case study projects.

Overall, respondents showed a preference for public engagement practices that are participatory and bottom-up. These need to be “genuine” and neutral spaces for deliberative, consensus-based

public consultations where people have valuable options for influencing the decision-making processes. These spaces must move away from box-ticking exercises like information meetings that only seek to increase social support and accelerate the implementation of the project. Instead, developers need to genuinely listen to community concerns before the design and development of the project, favouring informal settings so that local stakeholders can participate early in the process. In sum, findings in the three case studies point to three important factors affecting community acceptance of energy projects:

- 1) the degree to which people's concerns and views about the project are listened and attended too; opportunities for sharing concerns that consider ways in which people can feedback information to developers according to their culture and worldviews. This will require time flexibility to attain constructive deliberation processes, as well as avenues to promote the co-design, co-production, and co-ownership of renewable energy projects with local communities.
- 2) the degree to which governance structures facilitate, guarantee, and strengthen these spaces for inclusion in decision-making.
- 3) the extent to which the industry understands, engages, and integrates different identities and culture in their everyday practices and decisions (including the way the industry approaches, respects and follows local understandings of land ownership and collective decision-making, while considering historical contexts of industrialisation and colonisation).

5 Conclusion

By operationalising the energy justice framework, this deliverable considered notions of justice and injustice among the different actors in each case study, as well as their claims for inclusion in decision-making and for the recognition of their identities and interests. The report aimed at illuminating how these justice implications relate to the acceptance of energy technologies. It also looked at how pre-existing power relations dictate how acceptance contexts are shaped. An energy justice approach was instrumental in characterising what kind of informational channels and participation processes people on the ground have reason to value, given their history and culture, and in highlighting the importance of acknowledging and valuing local identities. The deliverable feeds into Deliverable 2 of Work Package 4, which applies these views of 'energy justice' and synthesises the key findings from the three foundational case studies into a framework of factors impacting the social acceptability of energy projects.

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Appendix 1 List of Interviewees

<i>Code</i>	<i>Role / Perspective</i>	<i>Case Study</i>
<i>CG1</i>	Solidarity worker	Corrib Gas
<i>CG2</i>	Academic	Corrib Gas
<i>CG3</i>	Citizen / Environmental activist	Corrib Gas
<i>CG4</i>	Citizen / Environmental activist	Corrib Gas
<i>CG5</i>	Citizen / Environmental activist	Corrib Gas
<i>CG6</i>	Citizen / Environmental activist	Corrib Gas
<i>CG7</i>	Citizen / Environmental activist	Corrib Gas
<i>GL1</i>	Citizen	Grid Link
<i>GL2</i>	Citizen	Grid Link
<i>GL3</i>	Journalist	Grid Link
<i>GL4</i>	Non-governmental organisation representative	Grid Link
<i>T1</i>	Municipality Director	Ternitz
<i>T2</i>	Citizen / Environmental Councillor	Ternitz
<i>T3</i>	Citizen / Retired Chemist	Ternitz
<i>T4</i>	Municipality Director	Ternitz